

**PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS' UNDERSTANDING OF SUSTAINABILITY
EDUCATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY**

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Abstract: *The implementation of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has become a global priority, yet it remains limited in teaching practices, particularly in developing countries like Pakistan. The purpose of the research is to explore prospective teachers' understanding of Sustainable Development (SD) and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). A qualitative phenomenological research design was adopted to gain in-depth insights from the participants' lived experiences. The study was conducted with 12 prospective teachers selected through purposive sampling from a teacher education program of a public university at Sialkot, Pakistan. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis. Three sub-themes extracted from the data were; Sustainability as intergenerational environmental responsibility, sustainability as a three-pillar systems framework and sustainability as social justice and equality. The findings indicate that the prospective teachers have a relatively good understanding of the sustainability concept in relation to the three interrelated dimensions of environmental, social, and economic development. The research also highlighted critical gaps in teacher education programs, particularly the absence of a systematic approach to sustainability training. The study concludes that although prospective teachers are motivated and conceptually prepared to teach sustainability, they are inadequately supported by the existing teacher education systems. It suggests integrating ESD across multiple domains in teacher education curricula, promoting experimental-based learning approaches, reforming assessment practices, and enhancing institutional and policy-level support.*

Keywords: Education for Sustainable Development, Prospective Teachers, Sustainability in Education, SDG 4.7, Teacher Education policy.

Introduction

The rise in environmental crises of the twenty-first century has made sustainability a global priority. The issues of climate change, deforestation, water scarcity, pollution, and biodiversity loss have created unparalleled threats to a better ecological system. Education for Sustainable Development refers to the teaching approaches and learning practices that may further help learners in developing knowledge, skills, and ethical values that relate to sustainability. ESD

encourages students to solve real-life problems, think critically, make decisions, and actively participate in every task. ESD helps to perform responsible actions related to environmental, social, and economic hurdles (Fischer et al., 2022).

Sustainable development means developing in a way that meets our needs today without harming the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The concept works like this, layer by layer: The Environment is the foundation for everything; society (people and communities) completely depends on a healthy environment to survive, and the economy completely relies on society to exist (Bezjeljak et al., 2020). Achieving these goals depends a lot on Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

The UN applies ESD not just in school subjects but also plays an important role in teaching and learning, which may later help individuals make decisions and solve problems (Corres et al., 2024). The study helps to examine and provide updated information about what prospective teachers currently know about sustainability, and as sustainability is a global need, teachers must know how to teach it in classrooms. Examining their beliefs is very important because the thinking of teachers strongly influences the practices in classrooms (Goller & Markert, 2025). However, research conducted in Pakistan and across the globe indicates that teacher preparation often fails to systematically integrate ESD concepts (Hinduja et al., 2023), resulting in an uneven or limited understanding among prospective teachers, even as sustainability and the SDGs are increasingly promoted in policy discourse. Pakistan has already shown its commitment to support the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Therefore, integrating sustainability ideas into what and how students are taught now, and into school curriculum and teaching methods, has become a top priority for the national policy goal (Batoool & e Habiba, 2021). Pakistan faces many environmental obstacles, including deforestation, air pollution, water scarcity, and climate vulnerability, all of which negatively affect sustainable practices (Öztürk et al., 2022). Lack of teacher training limited financial resources, and weak policy enforcement have further impeded the progress of sustainability initiatives in schools (Khadim et al., 2024). When prospective teachers have a definite understanding of sustainability, maybe by combining it purely with environmental conservation, they may not fully subscribe to the integrative, socioeconomic status, and values-driven capacity that ESD requires (Martín-Sánchez et al., 2022). The classroom behaviour and implementation of teachers and prospective teachers are outstandingly affected by their beliefs. They affect teachers' ethics, the significance of the subject matter, and pedagogical standards (Ahmed et al., 2025). If future generations use the resources of sustainable development wisely, they can also easily meet their own needs. The main aim of sustainable development is to keep both the economy and the environment strong and stable for the long term. This can only happen if we consider economic, environmental, and social issues together when deciding (Ferguson et al., 2021).

Research Objective

- To explore prospective teachers' understanding of the concept and purpose of sustainability education.

Literature Review

The goal of every society is to improve and to think about the well-being of its people. One of the most important goals of humanity in the 21st century is to construct a sustainable society. Education plays an important role in different ways. Firstly, it helps to build a sustainable and responsible society, and secondly, getting a good quality of education is itself one of the most important goals of a sustainable society. Sustainable development has very old roots (Bezjeljak et al., 2020).

Prospective teachers are the future of our education system. Because of this, they are the most important group to focus on when trying to bring Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) into schools. How these future teachers understand sustainability, how meaningful they think it is, and how confident they feel about using new teaching methods will greatly shape how well ESD works in Pakistan in the years to come (Jamil et al., 2024). It is hard to understand their approach to sustainability, how much they value it, and how comfortable they are teaching it to students. It is necessary to check their ideas and understanding regarding how to teach sustainability (Durrani et al., 2023). The study, conducted at the Universities of Ljubljana and Vienna, involved 120 pre-service biology teachers (60 from each country) who completed a questionnaire with Likert-type and open-ended questions (Bezjak et al., 2020).

If the prospective teacher does not have a proper understanding of sustainability, they may face difficulties in integrating sustainability education into classrooms. The study will analyze how prospective teachers perceive the concept of SD and ESD, what teaching methods they are supposed to use, and what obstacles they will face. The findings help to recognize the weak points in teacher training and guide policymakers and practices to improve (Martín-Sánchez et al., 2022). As a developing country, Pakistan faces many problems related to sustainable development that are very complex. These problems may include a shortage of clean water, being easily affected by extreme weather, fast population growth, and the last one is a big difference between rich and poor people.

Because of these urgent challenges, putting Education Sustainable Development (ESD) into the national education system is not just following a global trend; it's a vital step for the country to solve its own specific, pressing social, economic, and environmental problems (Khadim et al., 2024). Trying to comprehend how student-teachers conceptualized sustainability in the context of education and development, in a way that meets our needs today, without harming the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Afzaal et al., 2025).

Schools act as agents of developing ecological awareness in learners. Studies show that integrating sustainable practices in education helps students build habits that might inspire their surroundings, i.e., their family and community. School leaders can implement eco-friendliness through a series of action plans (Pauw et al., 2022). This goal cannot be achieved with a single step. Leaders synchronize the eco-friendly curriculum with the school culture. They integrate green values into the curriculum and promote initiatives like environmental literacy and zero-waste programs.

Studying teachers' beliefs provides updated information about what prospective teachers currently know about sustainability, and as sustainability is a global need, teachers must know how to teach it in classrooms. Examining their beliefs is very important because the thinking of teachers strongly influences the practices in classrooms (Malik et al., 2022).

Prospective teacher students currently studying in B.Ed. and other teacher training programs are the future of our education system. Because of this, they are the most important group to focus on when trying to bring Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) into schools. How these future teachers understand sustainability, how meaningful they think it is, and how confident they feel about using new teaching methods will greatly shape how well ESD works in Pakistan in the years to come (Jamil et al., 2024). For the implication of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and the global goals, it all comes down to what teachers can do and how committed they are. Teachers are the main agents of change who turn global goals into real learning experiences in the classroom lessons and activities. It may further help students to become responsible citizens of society and future decision-makers who play a role as future leaders (Shariq et al., 2025).

Research Methodology

The study was based on a qualitative phenomenology research design to explore how prospective teachers understand the concept of SD and ESD. This design focuses on participants' lived experiences with a particular phenomenon (Creswell & Poth, 2016). The sample for this study comprises prospective teachers from the Public University of Sialkot. A Purposive sampling technique was used to select 12 participants who were chosen by the judgment of the researcher, aiming to recruit information-rich participants. This is the sampling technique in which researchers select participants based on their belief that their responses will meet the objectives of the study (Obilor, 2023). Semi-structured interviews were used for data collection, which provide a structural context while allowing the participants to express their life experiences, understandings, and reflective points in their own words. Interview questions were developed to explore prospective teachers' understanding of sustainable education and education for sustainable development perceptions about purpose and their views about the importance of sustainability in teacher education (Cassell & Symon, 2004). Interviews lasted for about 30-40 minutes and were audio-recorded with consent. Data were transcribed verbatim and analyzed. The reflexive thematic data analysis technique was used to analyze the data. Reflexive Thematic Analysis is the action of analyzing figures or questions in qualitative data (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). The main aim of the reflexive thematic analysis was to make figures and questions, and to determine whether arrangements of the data are essential or not, and these figures are used to answer the research questions (Clarke & Braun, 2013). Data were analyzed using Reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), involving familiarization of data, coding, development of themes, review, and interpretation.

Findings

Based on the objective, the following theme was extracted from the data.

Theme 1: Conceptual Understanding of Sustainability Education

All twelve participants looked at sustainability education from three interlinked perspectives: the environment, society, and the economy. However, there was variation in terms of how these three dimensions were interpreted. The level of understanding of some interviewees focused largely on the environmental aspect and almost amounted to equating sustainability education with waste management and conservation of nature. On the other hand, some interviewees demonstrated a well-rounded understanding of sustainability education by factoring in such concepts as social justice and economic development. The following are further sub-themes.

Sustainability as Intergenerational Environmental Responsibility

The dominant perception in the beginning was that sustainability meant meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The previous perceptions seemed to be mainly about environmental issues such as saving water, planting trees, and recycling, which implies that this was how sustainability was perceived initially. Participant No. 1 gave a detailed and structured explanation of sustainability as the responsible use of both environmental and social resources:

The resources we use in the present — don't misuse them, and also restore them for future generations. We try to meet present needs without compromising the abilities of future generations. It may include a forest, which also has a great impact on our environment. We have to grow more plants and trees instead of cutting them down. The other element is water; we don't have to waste water. We have to avoid draining factory waste into clean water. If we don't avoid it, we will have a shortage of clean water in the future. We compromise all for the future generation.

Participant No. 4 offered a memorable and original framing of sustainability as "everlasting benefits" for both present and future people:

I think the shortest definition of sustainability is that things last forever, in one word, Everlasting Benefits. Benefits are not only for the present people but also for future people, without any harm to future people. If we are performing an activity, it should provide everlasting benefits. For example, if we are doing a plantation, then we should not just leave the plantation. In fact, we should also take care of their sustainability. When we take care of it, it will benefit the present people. The oxygen level will be better, and the environmental conditions will be better. Apart from that, future people, when those trees grow, will also benefit in the same way.

Participant No. 11 articulated a more structured academic understanding of sustainability that includes its three dimensions in relation to responsible citizenship:

Sustainability education means teaching students how to protect the environment, use natural resources responsibly, and work towards a better future for the next generations. It focuses on developing awareness about environmental protection and the importance of conserving resources. Students are educated on concepts such as pollution, global warming, and conservation through sustainability education. This education encourages critical thinking and wise decision-making in regard to sustainable development.

Sustainability as a Three-Pillar Systems Framework

A considerable number of the interviewees were initially inclined towards having an environmental outlook, and quite a few of them later came up with a broader view which would involve the use of such terms as economic and social together with environmental. They understood that sustainability was a systematic notion involving several interrelated pillars. Participant No. 9 exhibited a remarkable comprehensiveness in such an understanding of the topic at the system level:

While I knew the concept of sustainability before, I did not know what it had to do with the environment before. I did not know that sustainability had anything to do with society and the economy as well. Now, however, I have realized that it is about the social aspects and that we need to preserve them. Furthermore, we need to maintain sustainability in our economy as well, if our country is supposed to develop. The three aspects of mine are social, economic, and environmental, and our nation will thrive as long as they are preserved.

Participant No. 3 made a connection between sustainability and more social responsibility by mentioning environmental consciousness, wildlife conservation, and pollution control as relevant issues in Pakistan.

Considering the climate change and global warming scenario, I can say it has become an extremely important need nowadays. I think it is essential for us to realize the significance of sustainable actions. Sustainable actions may be defined as such acts that we undertake in order to keep the environment clean and green without using plastic bottles or anything that contains plastic in its composition, besides realizing the methods of recycling.

Participant No. 7 is demonstrating an understanding of sustainability in different aspects, like economic skills, environmental awareness, and social values, which were equally balanced in sustainability education as follows:

We can recycle and reuse the material. There is an economic element as well. When it comes to the economic element, we give our young ones skills. We make them more skilled for the sake of future generations to come. They have the capacity to contribute to the economy. The awareness element lies in

the environmental element. Our young ones must know how to plant. They need to learn about environmental responsibility as well. In the social element, we give our children social values.

Sustainability as Social Justice and Equality

The relationship between sustainability and social justice, gender equity, and equality was another important factor that separated the two. The participants did not restrict themselves to the ecological definition but argued that sustainability in its true sense is all about social justice and respect for everyone, irrespective of their class, caste, and gender. Participant No. 5 linked sustainability education directly to gender justice and civic equality:

There can be justice, social awareness, equality, and gender equality. Earlier, there was a lot of gender disparity, but now there is awareness among people, and such education is being provided to students. Gender disparity has decreased; now, gender equality is being promoted.

Participant No. 9 critiqued the unequal social treatment of poor people through the lens of sustainability, drawing on Islamic ethics to frame equality as a sustainability principle:

I think we should listen to the social factors. If we do it according to the principles, then our cultural diversity will increase. We don't want to see that someone is above or below. We should keep it sustainable. Who do we say is poor? We give examples of the poor and the rich. We don't like poor people. We differentiate. We don't want equality in that. We should bring equality.

Conclusion

This study explored the understandings of twelve BS Education prospective teachers in Sialkot, Pakistan, regarding sustainability education and its implications for teacher education policy. The findings demonstrate that prospective teachers hold developing and, in many cases, substantive conceptions of sustainability that span environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The study makes three significant contributions. First, it provides empirical evidence on prospective teachers' ESD understandings from a Pakistani public university context, which has been significantly underrepresented in the international ESD literature. Second, it reveals the culturally specific dimensions of sustainability understanding in Pakistan, including the integration of Islamic ethics, social justice, and community responsibility that must inform the design of ESD curricula and training programs. Third, it generates concrete, participant-grounded policy recommendations that can directly inform reforms in teacher education, school curriculum, and sustainability assessment in Pakistan. It can be concluded that prospective teachers in Pakistan are ready and motivated to teach sustainability, but they are being systemically under-prepared by the institutions and programs that train them. This gap is not inevitable. With deliberate curriculum reform, structured professional training, institutional support, and culturally responsive pedagogical frameworks, Pakistan's teacher education system can fulfil its critical role in advancing Education for Sustainable Development toward the 2030 Agenda.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal that prospective teachers in Pakistan possess developing but genuinely meaningful understandings of sustainability education that broadly correspond to the established three-pillar framework of sustainable development. This is consistent with Bezeljak et al. (2020), whose study of pre-service biology teachers in Slovenia and Austria found that most student teachers understood sustainable development primarily through the lens of environmental protection, but showed varying levels of awareness about its social and economic dimensions. The present study confirms this pattern while also revealing that

Pakistani prospective teachers, particularly those who have engaged with formal sustainability coursework, can articulate system-level, integrative understandings that connect all three pillars to national development challenges.

The variation in participants' conceptualizations, from narrow environmental to comprehensive systems-based understandings, mirrors the typology of conceptions identified in the global ESD literature. Ferguson et al. (2021) similarly found that teachers' perspectives on sustainable development ranged from simplified, nature-focused definitions to more complex, justice-oriented understandings, and that these conceptual differences directly influenced their pedagogical approaches in the classroom. Participants in the present study who held more integrative understandings, such as Participant No. 9, who linked economic sustainability to national development and social sustainability to equality, were also those who articulated richer pedagogical ideas and more policy-relevant recommendations. This suggests that the depth of conceptual understanding is a meaningful predictor of the quality and breadth of teaching practice, a finding that reinforces the importance of investing in the quality of sustainability education at the pre-service level.

Notably, several participants in this study explicitly linked sustainability to religious and cultural responsibility, connecting environmental stewardship to Islamic ethics, civic duty, and community obligation. This culturally embedded framing is significant for the Pakistani context, where religion and community identity are powerful motivators of behavior. Shariq et al. (2025) similarly found that teachers in Pakistan who connected sustainability to Islamic values and community responsibility were more motivated and effective as change agents for SDG integration. This finding suggests that ESD pedagogy in Pakistan should be designed to resonate with cultural and religious frameworks rather than presenting sustainability as a purely secular or Western concept.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are offered.

- All BS and MS-level programs should include a formal, structured course in sustainability education.
- Teacher educators should model the kind of active, participatory pedagogy they want prospective teachers to use, creating classrooms where sustainability is lived and practiced rather than merely discussed.
- School principals should protect time in the timetable for sustainability projects, plantation drives, recycling activities, and community engagement programs.
- School leaders should establish and enforce environmental norms, such as proper waste disposal, energy conservation, and care for school grounds, that make sustainability visible as an institutional value rather than an individual preference.
- Teachers in all disciplines should identify and use the sustainability dimensions of their subject areas, as illustrated by participants who linked Urdu composition, science ecosystems, and Islamic ethics to sustainability principles.
- Curriculum materials should reflect the social, religious, and environmental realities of Pakistani students, including climate threats specific to Pakistan, Islamic frameworks of environmental stewardship, and locally relevant sustainability challenges.

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